

Synthesis and Reactions of 2,3,5-pyrrolidinetriones

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The synthesis of some new 2,3,5-pyrrolidinetriones by the condensation of diethyl oxalate with substituted amides is reported. Some of their reactions have also been studied.

Although a number of pyrrolidinediones are known in literature, very little data is available about pyrrolidinetriones¹⁻⁴. The present communication reports the synthesis of a few new 2,3,5-pyrrolidinetriones (Table I) by the condensation of diethyl oxalate with different substituted amides in the presence of sodium ethoxide according to the general method described in literature^{3,5}. The amides were obtained from the corresponding known acid chlorides or the nitriles. The method succeeds with many amides and acetanilides although it fails with acetoacetamide and chloroacetamide. The failure of the last two is probably due to the electron withdrawing groups which cause easy hydrolysis followed by other reactions of the resulting acids formed in the presence of alkali.

- a) R = H; R₁ = C₆H₃(OCH₃)₂ (3,4)
- b) R = C₆H₅; R₁ = C₆H₅
- c) R = H; R₁ = CONH₂
- d) R = C₆H₄(CH₃) (4); R₁ = C₆H₅
- e) R = C₆H₅; R₁ = C₆H₃(OCH₃)₂ (3,4)
- f) R = C₆H₄(CH₃) (4); R₁ = C₆H₃(OCH₃)₂ (3,4)
- g) R = C₆H₄(OCH₃) (4); R₁ = C₆H₃(OCH₃)₂ (3,4)
- h) R = C₆H₅; R₁ = C₆H₃(-O-CH₂-O-) (3,4)

* Abstracted from Ph.D. thesis, 1967 Bombay University.

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It has been reported⁴ that pyrrolidinetriones having strong electron attracting groups in the 4-position possess the ability to form stable salts or complexes with a variety of metal ions. Accordingly, copper and nickel complexes of the general formula $(I)_2R$, where R is the metal ion were prepared from the triones Ic⁴ and Ih. The former was reacted as its monosodium salt⁴ while the latter was added directly, without isolation of the sodium salt to the hot metallic salt solution to obtain the complexes.

The triones give a bluish green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and also form acetyl derivatives. However, attempts to prepare an oxime or a 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative from Ih were unsuccessful. The failure to form these derivatives may be attributed to the strong enolisation and also to some extent to steric hindrance. It is interesting to note that 4-aryl-2,3-pyrrolidinediones also do not form oximes or dinitrophenylhydrazones. The triones Ia and Ih gave a quinoxaline derivative by condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine.

The i.r. spectrum of a typical pyrrolidinetrione showed bands at 3375 (NH), 1800–1700 (CO) cm^{-1} .

The n.m.r. spectrum (CDCl_3) of Id is consistent with its structure and showed peaks at δ 2.35 (3H, s- CH_3); δ 7.2–7.4 (7H, m, aromatic protons); δ 8.0–8.15 (3H, m, H and aromatic protons).

EXPERIMENTAL

General method for the preparation of 2,3,5-pyrrolidinetriones: Sodium (1.0 g.) was pulverised in xylene (60 ml.). To this was added absolute alcohol (7 ml.) at 60° during half hr. After the sodium had reacted the mixture was distilled to remove the excess of alcohol.

TABLE I

Amide (g.)	Pyrrolidine trione	M.P.	Analysis %			
			Found C	H	Required C	H
1. 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl-acetamide ⁹ (4.0)	Ia (2.0.)	284–86	58.0	4.5	57.8	4.5
2. Phenylacetanilide ⁷ (12.6)	Ib (8.0)	191	72.1	4.2	72.4	4.1
3. Phenylacetyl- <i>p</i> -toluidine ⁸ (4.7)	Id (2.0)	186–87	73.1	4.7	72.8	4.5
4. 3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl-acetanilide ⁹ (5.0)	Ie (3.0)	239–40	66.6	4.8	66.5	4.6
5. 3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl-acetyl- <i>p</i> -toluidine ⁹ (5.9)	If (5.2)	213–14	67.8	5.3	67.5	5.0
6. 3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl-acetyl- <i>p</i> -anisidine ⁹ (6.3)	Ig (2.8)	209–10	63.9	4.9	64.2	4.8
7. 3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl-acetanilide ^{10,11} (5.3)	Ih (2.6)	195–96	65.4	3.8	65.8	3.9

All compounds as yellow needles from methanol except Ib from alcohol and Id from benzene.

u.v. in MeOH λ_{max} . log (ϵ); Ia, 262 (4.23); 400 (3.55); Id, 255 (4.33), 420 (3.46); Ie, 265 (4.55), 420 (3.63); Ig, 270 (4.27), 420 (3.33); Ih, 268 (4.59), 425 (3.77).

After cooling the reaction mixture to 80° the amide was added and when the temperature was 60° , diethyl oxalate (3.3 g.) was added during 10 mins. The alcohol from the reaction mixture was removed with some xylene by slowly distilling it over a period of 3 hr. The residue was mixed with a large excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 ml.) and ice (15 g.). The yellow solid which separated was filtered and washed with water and xylene alternatively. (Table I).

Condensation of triones with o-phenylenediamines : A mixture of Ia (249 mg.) and o-phenylenediamine (110 mg.) in acetic acid (5 ml.) was refluxed for 1.5 hr. The yellow solid obtained on cooling was crystallised from acetic acid in fine needles, m.p. $268-69^\circ$. (Found : N, 12.9, $C_{18}H_{15}N_3O_3$ requires N, 13.1%).

Similarly Id (279 mg.) gave 250 mg. of the quinoxaline derivative crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. $287-88^\circ$. (Found : N, 12.1, $C_{23}H_{13}N_3O$ requires : N, 12.0%).

Preparation of 4-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(4-tolyl)-2,5-diketo-3-acetoxy- Δ^3 -pyrroline : A mixture of If (340 mg.), acetic anhydride (3 ml.) and pyridine (2-3 drops) was refluxed for half hr. and poured into cold water. The pasty mass obtained solidified on keeping overnight in a refrigerator. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate to yield yellow prisms (300 mg.), m.p. $173-74^\circ$. (Found : N, 3.5, $C_{21}H_{19}NO_6$ requires : N, 3.7%).

Reaction of Ic with $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$: The monosodium salt of Ic⁴ (0.01 mole) was dissolved in hot water (60 ml.) and filtered. To this solution heated on a water bath was added a filtered solution of $CuSO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ (0.0055 mole) with stirring. The metal complexes began separating immediately. After addition the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and the copper complex (1.5 g.) was collected, washed with water and dried overnight under vacuum. (Found : Cu, 16.8, $(C_5H_3N_2O_4)Cu \cdot H_2O$ requires Cu, 16.2%).

Reaction of Ic with $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$: The reaction was carried out as before to give the nickel complex. (Found : Ni, 12.8, $(C_5H_3N_2O_4)Ni \cdot 4H_2O$ requires Ni, 13.3%).

Reaction of Ih with $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$: Ih (0.012 mole) was added to a solution of sodium (23 mg.) in alcohol (10 ml.) and the reaction carried out as before to give the copper complex (2.4 g.). (Found : Cu, 8.6, $(C_{17}H_{10}NO_5)_2Cu \cdot H_2O$ requires : Cu, 9.1%).

Reaction of Ih with $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$: The nickel complex (2.5 g.) was obtained as above. (Found : Ni, 7.5, $(C_{17}H_{10}NO_5)_2Ni \cdot 4H_2O$ requires : Ni, 7.9%).

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